
The Impact of Social Media on Mental Health: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

This review paper investigates the relationship between social media usage and mental health, emphasizing its dual nature as both a facilitator of social connectivity and a potential source of psychological distress, particularly among adolescents. The methodology involves literature review of peer-reviewed articles published between 2000 and 2024, focusing on the positive and negative impacts of social media. Findings reveal that while social media platforms like Facebook and Instagram can foster connections and enhance communication, they are also associated with adverse mental health outcomes, including increased anxiety, depression, and feelings of loneliness. Moreover, factors such as the quality of online interactions and engagement in negative social comparisons are significant in determining mental health outcomes. The review highlights the need for effective interventions, including educational programs and parental engagement, to mitigate the negative effects of social media while promoting its positive aspects. The insights gained from this research are intended to inform policymakers, educators, and mental health professionals in developing strategies that support healthy social media use among young people.

1. Introduction

Humans are inherently social beings who rely on relationships with others to flourish. As such, maintaining social connections can reduce stress, anxiety, and depression, whereas a lack of these connections can significantly harm mental health (Mohammad, et. al., 2018).

In the last decade, the swift rise of social networking platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram has brought about notable shifts in the way individuals interact and communicate. With over a billion active users, Facebook is the largest social networking site, and its user base is expected to expand further, particularly in developing nations. Facebook serves as a tool for both personal and professional connections, contributing positively to communication, knowledge exchange, and online education (Pantic, 2014).

Mental health is described as a condition of well-being where individuals understand their capabilities, handle everyday obstacles effectively, perform well in their jobs, and positively impact the lives of others (Karim et. al, 2020).

In today's world, one of the most noticeable traits of teenagers is their frequent use of social media. Staying connected with others, whether at home, school, or social events, is a common practice, and teens are regularly interacting with their peers through social media platforms. The appeal of social networking sites for adolescents lies in the ability to share photos, images, and videos on these platforms. Studies indicate that there is a link between increased social networking and depressive symptoms in adolescents. Previous research has consistently demonstrated a link between mobile device use before bedtime and diminished sleep quality. This includes shorter sleep durations, lower sleep quality, and increased daytime fatigue. A widely recognized advantage of social media is its ability to foster social connection (Khalaf, 2023).

According to Berryman (2018), The use of social media plays a crucial role in the developmental journey of youth and young adults as they engage with others and showcase their evolving identities online. The findings from various studies on the impact of social media on mental health have been quite varied. While the prevailing public discourse often suggests that simple exposure to social media correlates with mental health problems, the most compelling evidence indicates that the quality of usage is more significant than the amount of time spent online. For example, research has shown that engaging in negative social comparisons on social media, combined with rumination, can lead to increased depression. Conversely, other studies reveal that positive interactions on social media, such as authentic self-representation, are linked to enhanced well-being among users. This perspective—that the manner in which social media is utilized may be more important than mere exposure—contrasts with much of the alarmist public narrative and deserves further exploration.

In 2020, approximately 3.8 billion people around the world were using social media, which accounts for about half of the global population. Recent research indicates that individuals with mental health disorders are increasingly accessing and utilizing mobile devices like smartphones. Likewise, a recent study revealed that individuals with severe mental illnesses who are receiving community-based mental health services use social media at rates comparable to the general population, with over 70% of participants engaging in it (Naslund, 2020).

In recent years, numerous parents, advocates, and policymakers have voiced concerns about the possible adverse effects of social media usage. Certain studies suggest that social media use may be linked to negative mental health issues, such as suicidality, feelings of loneliness, and reduced empathy. However, other research has either found no evidence of harm or suggested that social media use can be beneficial for some individuals (Berryman, 2018). The aim of this study is to review the positive and negative impact of social media on mental health.

2. Methodology

This review paper employs a comprehensive literature reviews to explore the intricate relationship between social media usage and mental health outcomes. The process begins with a search of relevant academic databases, including Google Scholar, using targeted keywords such as "social media," "mental health," "adolescents," and "psychological well-being from secondary sources." The inclusion criteria encompass studies published from 2000 to 2024, focusing on peer-reviewed articles that address both the positive and negative impacts of social media on mental health. This methodology aims to establish a balanced perspective on the implications of social media use, identifying both the potential benefits and the risks associated with its pervasive influence on mental health. The findings from this review was to inform policymakers, educators, and mental health professionals about effective strategies to mitigate risks and promote positive online interactions among adolescents.

3. Discussion

3.1 The Positive Impact of Social Media on Mental Health

Social media refers to any digital platform that allows users to quickly create and share content with the public. Various applications and websites, including Snapchat, Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok, are designed specifically for sharing photos and videos (Kaur et al., 2022).

The extensive use of the internet and social media presents opportunities for innovation, social interaction, and learning. However, policymakers and public health researchers have started to express concerns about the potential effects on the mental well-being of young people (Kaur et al., 2022).

Social media is a vital aspect of individual lives, influencing our personal experiences and significantly affecting our culture, economy, and overall well-being. It serves as a platform for people to share ideas, connect with others, relate to different perspectives, seek advice, and provide support (Kaur et al., 2022).

Research in developmental psychology has firmly established that robust peer relationships, social skills, and support networks are crucial for preventing mental health issues and promoting overall psychological well-being (Keenan et. al., 2016).

The need for social connectivity was highlighted across various groups, as both adolescents and practitioners noted the potential advantages of social media in reducing feelings of isolation, enhancing social skills, and facilitating ongoing communication (O'Reilly, 2020).

Friendship was highlighted as a crucial element of adolescent life, and social media was identified as a tool that helps maintain these friendships, especially when physical distance poses a challenge. The social dimension of social media was underscored, with some individuals noting that its use enhances their social skills (O'Reilly, 2020).

The Hearty Soul (2016) claims that spending more time on social media is associated with increased feelings of depression. Additionally, it reports that using social networking apps like Facebook and Twitter is less effective for students in maintaining focus and reducing stress.

According to O'Keeffe & Clarke-Pearson (2011), Participation in social media can provide adolescents with significant advantages that influence their self-perception, sense of community, and worldview. These benefits include:

- Opportunities for community involvement, such as fundraising for charities and participating in local political and philanthropic events.
- Enhanced creativity, both individually and collectively, through the development and sharing of artistic and musical projects.
- The generation of new ideas through the creation of blogs, podcasts, videos, and gaming platforms.
- The ability to expand online connections with others who share similar interests, allowing for interactions with people from diverse backgrounds. This kind of communication is crucial for adolescents, as it promotes respect, tolerance, and deeper discussions about personal and global matters.
- The encouragement of personal identity development and the enhancement of social skills.

Following Figure 1 visualizing the positive effects of social media on mental health by gender, based on a March 2024 survey. It shows that 9% of men reported "Very Positive" effects, compared to 6% of women, and 16% of men reported "Somewhat Positive" effects, compared to 15% of women.

Source: Statista (2024)

Figure 1: Positive effects of social media on mental health by gender.

An increasing amount of research indicates that social media usage is linked to negative health outcomes. While the connection between social media use and health especially mental health might be bidirectional, most public health studies concentrate on how social media usage affects health-related results (Bekalu et. al., 2019).

3.2. The Negative Impact of Social Media on Mental Health

Dick (2013) noted that while free social networking platforms like Facebook and Twitter help individuals stay connected with friends and access valuable content, they also result in a significant loss of privacy and discretion. In today's society, anxiety has become one of the primary mental health issues.

According to Kaur et al., (2022) Research indicates that social media use can have detrimental effects on adolescents. For instance, playing video games may lead to increased aggressive behavior in teenagers. Additionally, excessive internet use has been associated with various psychological and physical issues, including sleep deprivation, chronic fatigue, back and eye strain, social isolation, and a deficiency in real-life social interactions.

Umberson and Montez (2010) assert that both the quality and quantity of social relationships influence health behaviors, physical health, mental health, and the risk of mortality. Research consistently shows that using social media, particularly heavy use and extended periods spent on these platforms, seems to elevate the risk of various mental health symptoms and negatively impact overall well-being, particularly in young individuals. Social media usage can have harmful effects on the younger generation, as mental health issues that arise during youth can persist as lifelong challenges for individuals.

According to O'Keeffe & Clarke (2011), Youth using social media can face various risks, often more frequently than adults realize. These risks typically fall into categories such as peer interactions, inappropriate content, online privacy issues, and third-party advertising influences.

- **Cyberbullying** involves using digital platforms to share false or harmful information, leading to serious mental health impacts like depression, anxiety, and isolation. It's more common than online harassment and can affect any teen.
- **Sexting** refers to sending or receiving sexually explicit content via digital devices. About 20% of teens engage in this behavior, which can result in serious legal consequences, emotional distress, or school suspension. However, in some cases, it remains confined to small peer groups.
- **Facebook depression** describes depression triggered by extensive social media use, where preteens and teens become isolated or seek harmful behaviors due to the intense nature of online interactions.

3.3. To Mitigate the Negative Impact of Social Media on Mental Health

To mitigate these risks, appropriate measures should be implemented, such as organizing information and counseling sessions in schools and colleges. An effective awareness campaign can be established to help the younger generation understand the impact of social media use on mental health. Additionally, access to social networking sites should be restricted to specific age groups. Any social media platform that promotes negative behaviors, such as discrimination, violence, or racism, should be immediately shut down.

According to O'Keeffe & Clarke-Pearson (2011), Pediatricians can support parents in several specific ways:

- Encourage parents to engage their children and teenagers in conversations about their online activities and the challenges that today's youth encounter online.
- Recommend that parents address their own knowledge gaps regarding the various technologies their children are using.
- Talk to families about the importance of establishing a family online-use plan, which includes regular meetings to discuss online issues and review privacy settings and profiles for inappropriate content. The focus should be on promoting healthy online behavior and responsible citizenship rather than on punitive measures, unless absolutely necessary.
- Emphasize to parents the significance of actively supervising their children's online activities through involvement.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, the impact of social media on mental health is multifaceted, presenting both opportunities and challenges, particularly for adolescents. While social networking platforms can foster connections, enhance creativity, and provide a sense of community, they also pose significant risks, such as increased feelings of isolation, anxiety, and depression. The quality of interactions on these platforms appears to be more critical than the quantity of time spent online. Thus, it is essential for parents, educators, and policymakers to recognize the complexities of social media use and to implement strategies that promote healthy online behaviors. By prioritizing digital literacy, fostering open discussions about online experiences, and creating supportive environments, we can mitigate the adverse effects of social media while leveraging its potential to enhance social well-being. Further research is necessary to deepen our understanding of these dynamics and to develop targeted interventions that support mental health in the digital age.

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